

THE USE OF CALQUE IN THE TRANSLATION OF CROSS-CULTURAL DIFFERENCES

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Abstract. *The paper explores the concept of calque in linguistics, a process where words or phrases are translated literally from one language to another. Calques are a type of loan translation and represent a unique form of lexical borrowing that reflects both linguistic creativity and cross-cultural influence. The thesis discusses function of the calque in language development, translation studies, and intercultural communication.*

Key words: *cross-cultural differences, calque, loan translation, phraseological units, compound noun, cultural competence.*

A calque is a type of linguistic borrowing in which a word or phrase from one language is translated literally into another language by translating its individual components – such as morphemes, words, or parts of a compound – rather than borrowing the original foreign term in its phonetic form. The term comes from the French word calque, meaning “copy” or “tracing”. It reflects the idea that a calque is essentially a “tracing” or “imprint” of a foreign expression, but recreated using the vocabulary and grammatical structure of the borrowing language. So, a calque is not a direct borrowing of a word, like “pizza” from Italian. It is a translation-based borrowing, where the structure and meaning are kept, but the words themselves are in the target language. So it is a type of borrowing in linguistics where a word or phrase from one language is translated literally – part by part – into another language.

According to the linguist A.A.Reformatsky, calques consist of translating foreign words or phrases part-by-part... Thus, in calque, the combination of elements is borrowed, but the elements themselves are formed from the native language, not taken from the foreign source. Therefore, the calque method is particularly effective in translating idiomatic expressions and enriching the phraseological fund of a language [1, p. 117]. The scholar states that calque is used in the translation of the idioms and phraseological units effectively.

N.S. Arapova states that a calque is a word, phrase, or compound term that conveys a new meaning by being translated literally in a way that aligns with the existing language units of the target language [2, p. 211]. So calque is used for translating phraseological units and compound nouns.

It is well known that in studying the linguocultural features of phraseological units in structurally different languages (such as English and Uzbek), the use of translation techniques – particularly analogy and equivalence – helps determine the level of linguocultural compatibility between different nations. In this regard, the use of calque in translation practice proves to be more effective than other translation methods, especially when translating phraseological units and proverbs. The translator attempts to replicate the exact structure and lexical components of the source text in the target language. This often leads to the creation of new words and expressions in the target language. Calque is also used in the translation of compound nouns.

However, calque tends to expose cultural differences between the source and target languages. For example, a word or phrase may carry deep cultural significance in its source context, but it can be difficult to convey this meaning precisely in target language. Calque does not account for these cultural elements, and often distorts or overlooks the cultural context during the translation process. Particularly when the shared historical or social context between the two cultures is lacking, calque can result in ambiguity or inaccurate meanings in the translated text. For example, in the novel “O‘tkan kunlar” the word “qorachopon” is used [3, p. 84]. This word is a compound noun that carries a historical connotation. And it is calqued on “black robe” by Mark Reese [4, p. 84]. Also, in the translation of the novel, the Uzbek phraseological unit, “ko‘z ostidan kechirmoq”, calqued on “eyeing carefully” by Carol Ermakova [5, p. 18].

It is worth emphasizing that while phraseological units and compound nouns have been extensively studied from a comparative perspective using Uzbek and English language materials, their translation specifically through the lexical transformation named calque has not been adequately explored. We find it appropriate to reflect the theoretical basis of studying phraseological units from a linguocultural perspective in the following points: the translation of phraseological units play a significant role in enriching the phraseological fund of a national language; studying phraseological units as vivid means of expressing national culture, and conducting comparative research within the frameworks of two linguistically distinct systems (Uzbek and English), helps to more precisely identify their universal and language-specific features.

To sum up, the calque is effectively used in translation in the following situations: in the translation of phraseological units, in the translation of compound words, when translating a word, phrase, or expression literally into forms compatible with the target language, in the part-by-part translation of words or expressions.

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